

A Study on Workplace Ostracism and Job Outcomes

Vijay Vishwakarma

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3995-7913>

Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Bunts Sangha's, S M Shetty College of Science,
Commerce and Management studies, Powai, Mumbai

ABSTRACT

Purpose: *The aim of the paper is to identify and observe ostracism at the place of work and its outcome.*

Design/approach/Methodology- *Researcher has collected data from 156 employees of various organizations working at the Powai area concerning the Mumbai region. The author has proposed the relationship of employees at the workplace and its effect on Job tension, Job- satisfaction and devotion towards the organization.*

Findings: *Result has shown that there is a negative relation between workplace ostracism and Job tension, Job satisfaction and loyalty towards the organization.*

Practical implications: *Workplace ostracism has a high level of job tension. Ostracism is due to personal and environmental experiences that are related to negative outcomes i.e. Job satisfaction, loyalty, performance and so on.*

Also, the study gives a future scope to all the managers to pay more attention to the individual's attitude at the workplace. Managers can come up with various ways to minimize workplace ostracism by increasing employee psychological resources.

Keywords: *Ostracism, workplace, Job tension, Job satisfaction, loyalty.*

INTRODUCTION

Ostracism is nothing but ignoring the individual or individuals by an individual or individuals. (William 2007) .Various studies have shown that how ostracism is very stressful especially at the workplace which has a very bad impact on the performance of the employees. It has also resulted in bad food habits, an increase in the anxiety level, work pressure and so on. Ostracism has a bad impact on the process that can affect one's diet.

OBJECTIVES

- To examine the behavior of employees concerning workplace ostracism.
- To analyze the outcome of workplace ostracism

HYPOTHESES

- H1 Workplace ostracism is negatively related to Job tension.
- H2 Workplace ostracism is negatively related to Job satisfaction and commitment towards the organization.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Li, Y. C. (2019), The author has tried to find the gap in various literature. The study has shown ostracism at workplace has negatively associated with a psychological detachment which has resulted in a bad quality of sleep. The result has come by surveying 403 samples. The two factors have been mediated by psychological detachment. It has also compared with humor factor, which has resulted that employees may get affected due to workplace ostracism because of low humor.

Al-Atwi, A. A. (2017), Researcher has studied the effect of ostracism on employee procedure. In this paper, workplace ostracism, social relation and empowerment have been linked to the employee's output. It has tried to cover the various psychological effects of an employee. The study has also been done on How empowerment structures have acted as a mediator of the relationship between ostracism

and both in the role and extra-role performance. The researcher has proposed the future researcher for multilevel analysis.

Hakan, E., & Chafra, J. (2016), Researcher aims to identify the relationship between the behavior and workplace ostracism and also to test moderating behavior. The test has resulted in a negative relationship between leaders' behavior and workplace ostracism. The behavior of the leader was not so conducive that has resulted in a higher psychological distance.

HAQ, I. U. (2014), Researcher has analyzed the association between workplace ostracism, job performance, job stress, turnover. With the responses received from 229 respondents of various organizations of pakistan, it has shown a expressively positive relationship with job stress and a negative relationship with job performance. The researcher has also found that with high psychological capital, the relationship between workplace ostracism with job stress and turnover was very weak.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The Sample size for the study was 156 employees working in different industry holding positions at different levels. It was a purposive convenience sampling.

Primary Data: A questionnaire containing questions on different parameters on Ostracism was used to collect data from the employees of various organizations.

The statistical tool used: Ms excel (ANOVA, Descriptive statistics, Correlation)

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The researcher has analyzed and interpreted the data.

H1 Workplace ostracism is negatively related to Job tension.

To prove Workplace ostracism is negatively related to Job Tension, we came up with the following findings.

Questions

Column	Abbreviations- I remained silent because
1	I will not find a sympathetic, anyway
2	my superiors are not open to proposals, concerns, like
3	nothing will change, anyway
4	fear of negative consequences
5	not make me vulnerable in the face of colleagues or superiors.

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

	Column1	Column2	Column3	Column4	Column5
Mean	2.269230769	2.5	2.423076923	2.653846	2.346154
Standard Error	0.084998007	0.084095	0.089589848	0.091696	0.070243
Median	2	2.5	2	3	2
Mode	2	3	2	2	2
Standard Deviation	1.061624767	1.050346	1.118976846	1.145278	0.877341
Sample Variance	1.127047146	1.103226	1.252109181	1.311663	0.769727
Kurtosis	-0.088741789	-0.39349	0.074373228	-0.98239	-0.54403
Skewness	0.621902868	0.304558	0.782980404	0.085259	0.306132
Range	4	4	4	4	3
Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
Maximum	5	5	5	5	4
Sum	354	390	378	414	366
Count	156	156	156	156	156
Confidence Level(95.0%)	0.167903969	0.16612	0.176974633	0.181134	0.138758

ANOVA: Single Factor						
SUMMARY						
Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance		
1	155	353	2.277419355	1.123837		
1	155	389	2.509677419	1.095685		
2	155	376	2.425806452	1.25907		
2	155	412	2.658064516	1.317386		
2	155	364	2.348387097	0.773942		
ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	13.54064516	4	3.38516129	3.038788	0.016796	2.383496
Within Groups	857.7677419	770	1.11398408			
Total	871.3083871	774				

Interpretation: We conducted One-way Anova to know the significant difference between workplace ostracism and Job tension. It is observed that the p-value is 0.016796, which is less than 0.05. We conclude that Workplace ostracism is negatively related to Job tension.

Questions

Column	Abbreviations - Behaviour towards others at work
1	People make fun of others at work
2	People here often say something hurtful to others at work
3	People here often cursed others
4	People sometimes make an ethnic, religious or racial remark at work.
5	People here often act rudely towards others at work.
6	People here often publicly embarrass their colleagues

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

	Column1	Column2	Column3	Column4	Column5	Column6
Mean	3.192308	2.884615	2.615385	2.846154	2.384615	2.461538
Standard Error	0.080381	0.078215	0.092059	0.091017	0.074143	0.081032
Median	3	3	2	3	2	2
Mode	4	3	4	3	2	2
Standard Deviation	1.003962	0.976905	1.149819	1.136797	0.92605	1.012086
Sample Variance	1.00794	0.954342	1.322084	1.292308	0.857568	1.024318
Kurtosis	-0.30024	-0.70457	-1.48246	-0.62699	-0.70286	-0.08041
Skewness	-0.62802	-0.52264	0.022895	-0.01327	0.34359	0.559979
Range	4	3	3	4	3	4
Minimum	1	1	1	1	1	1
Maximum	5	4	4	5	4	5
Sum	498	450	408	444	372	384
Count	156	156	156	156	156	156
Confidence Level(95.0%)	0.158784	0.154505	0.181853	0.179793	0.146462	0.160069

ANOVA: Single Factor						
SUMMARY						
Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance		
3	155	495	3.193548	1.014244		
3	155	447	2.883871	0.960452		
1	155	407	2.625806	1.313615		
ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	25.04946	2	12.52473	11.42659	1.43E-05	3.015242

Within Groups	506.4	462	1.096104			
Total	531.4495	464				

Interpretation: We conducted One-way Anova to know the significant difference between workplace ostracism and Job tension. It is observed that the p-value is 1.43E-05, which is less than 0.05. We conclude that Workplace ostracism is negatively related to Job tension.

H2 Workplace ostracism is negatively related to Job satisfaction and loyalty towards the organization.

To prove Workplace ostracism is negatively related to Job satisfaction and loyalty towards the organization.

Questions

Column	Abbreviations
1	People here ignore me
2	People here often leave the area when I enter
3	My greetings have gone unanswered at work
4	I voluntarily sat alone in the crowded lunchroom at work
5	I have often noticed that others would not look at me at work
6	Others at work shut me out of the conversation
7	Others at work did not invite me or ask me if I wanted anything when they went out for tea coffee snacks to break.

	Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	Column 4	Column 5	Column 6	Column 7
Mean	2.192308	1.807692	2.153846	2.384615	2.461538	2.192308	2.076923
Standard Error	0.077233	0.066903	0.088248	0.107017	0.107373	0.083411	0.066546
Median	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Mode	2	2	1	1	2	2	2
Standard Deviation	0.964635	0.835621	1.102222	1.336638	1.341086	1.041806	0.831155
Sample Variance	0.930521	0.698263	1.214888	1.7866	1.798511	1.085366	0.690819
Kurtosis	-0.79358	1.273189	-0.11777	-0.68831	-0.82558	0.349603	-0.6834
Skewness	0.39084	1.182233	0.744383	0.644766	0.668385	0.85445	0.264282
Range	3	3	4	4	4	4	3
Minimum	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Maximum	4	4	5	5	5	5	4
Sum	342	282	336	372	384	342	324
Count	156	156	156	156	156	156	156
Confidence Level(95.0%)	0.152564	0.13216	0.174324	0.211399	0.212103	0.164769	0.131453

ANOVA: Single Factor						
SUMMARY						
Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance		
1	155	341	2.2	0.927273		
1	155	281	1.812903	0.698534		
1	155	335	2.16129	1.214076		
3	155	369	2.380645	1.795727		
2	155	382	2.464516	1.808798		
2	155	340	2.193548	1.092166		
1	155	323	2.083871	0.687725		
ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	41.22212	6	6.870353	5.847608	5.17E-06	2.106976
Within Groups	1266.542	1078	1.1749			
Total	1307.764	1084				

Interpretation: We conducted one-way Anova to know the significant difference between Job satisfaction and loyalty towards the organization. It is observed that the p-value is 5.17E-06, which is less than 0.05. We conclude that Workplace ostracism is negatively related to Job satisfaction and loyalty towards the organization.

CONCLUSION & SUGGESTIONS

From the above data, we hereby conclude that ostracism takes a great impression on Job satisfaction and Job loyalty which turns has led to Job tension in the organization. Results show that workplace ostracism is a foremost work stressor that affects the performance of employees at the workplace. Workforces have a great level of job tension concerning workplace ostracism. Ostracism is due to personal and environmental experiences that are related to negative outcomes i.e Job satisfaction, loyalty, performance and so on.

Also, the study gives a future scope to all the managers to pay more attention to the individual's attitude at the workplace. Managers can come up with various ways to minimize workplace ostracism by increasing employee psychological resources. Training to encourage psychological capital can be given to the managers to minimize ostracism at the workplace, Thus ostracism may consider a major threat for the organization as it is related to social separation anxiety and leads to sensitivity to attention.

Further research can be conducted to understand cognitive, affective and behavioral parts and to understand and frame a model that can help to lessen various psychological factors.

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